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Tracer Study BEED and BSED Graduates of Northwest Samar State University, Calbayog City

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ABSTRACT

Graduates are undecided on many things after disembarking one of the frontiers of their lives. They do not know if they will stagnate or be productive. But one thing for them is sure, they need to have a career. It was found out in the study that the personal profile of the BEED and BSED graduates were as follows: most of them were at the middle age, female, single, resided on places outside city proper, worked on places outside city proper but within Calbayog City, most of them are LET passers, some graduates are with academic honors and awardees and majority of the respondents have master's units. Most of them are permanently employed and mentioned that it is their first job after graduation. Most of the graduates are teaching in the major field and they are connected with the government units. Majority of the graduates find employment through application letter and they have waited for more than a year before landing to a job. There are different competencies demanded of from teacher education graduates such as socio – personal, intellectual, and technical competence. The major problem of the graduates in job hunting is on financial aspect. Therefore, the course offering of the College is commendable since it caters the need of the locality and demand for employment opportunities thereby giving better chances for graduates to find job and eventually alleviating the economic condition of every citizen. The kind of orientation makes them qualified to diverse job opportunities in the real world.

INTRODUCTION

“Do you know where you’re going to?” asked by Diana Ross in one of her popular singles is one true thing confronting everyone after graduation. Graduates are undecided on many things after disembarking one of the frontiers of their lives. They do not know if they will stagnate or be productive. But one thing for them is sure; they need to have a career.

With this, CHED closely monitors colleges offering education and accountancy and also the agency has gone through institutions offering maritime and nursing courses. Such monitoring is being conducted to see which schools have zero performance or no passers in licensure examinations in the last five years (Manila Bulletin, 2009). Aside from monitoring, CHED imposes moratorium on opening of new course programs in Teacher Education, Business Administration, Nursing, Hotel and Restaurant Management and Information Technology by virtue of CHED Memorandum Order 32 (Ronda, 2010). According to CHED Commissioner, there’s a need to stop more schools from opening the courses to prevent a worsening “oversupply” of graduates in the field because this cause some problems on the quality of their curriculum.

In all issues and controversies posed to State Universities and Colleges, the University in the locality is still stable in terms of enrolment despite all odds and challenges confronted every year. The College was able to maintain the prestige in its offering which consequently, attracted more students every school year. Eventually, there is enough number of prospective teachers produced by the College.

Objectives

The following are the objectives of the study:

1. Determine the personal profile of the BEED and BSED graduates
2. Determine the employment status of graduates in terms of the following:
 - 2.1 work status;
 - 2.2 nature of work;
 - 2.3 type of employment;
 - 2.4 manner of getting the job; and
 - 2.5 waiting time after graduation.
3. Describe the problems encountered by the graduates in job hunting.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Career planning is not planning for a field on a one-time only basis, but it’s a continuing process; in fact, you can call it a lifetime process. We are always learning and growing, and as we do, our interests and needs also change. Career planning is not just making plans to obtain your “perfect” job or career, but to help you make the many adjustments there will be along the way as you learn about you and your world or work (Hooley, Tristram & Marriott, John & Sampson, James, 2011)).

The Need Theory or Psychodynamic Theory proposed by Anne Roe (Villar, 2009) is one of the theories where the present study is anchored. According to this theory, early childhood experiences are the root of career directions and satisfaction. Thus, it is very important to consider the parental styles provided by parents, the general background and the socio-economic status of one’s family.

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Furthermore, this theory emphasized that needs have a strong bearing on personal interests, self-concept and personal orientation. With this, it should be realized that lower needs are satisfied before higher order needs. On the present study, the researcher believes that a graduate lands a job to satisfy his immediate needs.

On the other hand, the theory on Life Span or Self-Concept Theory advanced by Donald Super (Villar, 2009) states that the process of career development involves developing and implementing occupational self-concepts through synthesis and compromise. He added that abilities and characteristics are so immense that everyone has the necessary qualifications to become successful in many occupations and this makes people qualify for many different occupations.

While Development Theory proposed by Eli Ginzberg (Villar, 2009) described that there are four factors that influence career development. These are reality, educational process, emotional factor and individual values. The first factor talks about the ability to handle pressures and constraints in a chosen career path; the second factor considers the proper educational preparation in order to succeed in the desired career; the third factor emphasizes the emotional security as basis for determining satisfaction; and the fourth factor poses individual differences in the attainment of happiness.

METHODS

This study utilized mainly the descriptive survey to describe the profile of the graduates in relation to the status of employment as it exists at the time of the study and explored the course of this issue using a questionnaire. The questionnaire assessed the personal profile of BEED and BSED graduates. The graduates were asked also on their perceptions about the extent of influence of the different variables such as socio – personal competence, intellectual competence and technical competence to employability of teacher education graduates. The survey instrument likewise asked the graduate-respondents for problems encountered in searching for a job and problems in their present occupations.

The whereabouts of the graduate-respondents were gathered from the school records of the Registrar’s Office. Other additional information such as current address of the graduates will be solicited from other school personnel and from other students and their

friends who happened to know their latest situation.

The questionnaire was composed of three parts: Part I – The profile of the respondents which included the personal data as to their name, age, sex, civil status, place of residence, place of work, year graduated, course/field of specialization, eligibility, honors received and advanced education. Part II - Employment status, it included the work status, nature of work, type of work, manner of getting the job, waiting time after graduation. Part III – This part of the questionnaire provided the perception of the graduates on the influence of factors such as socio – personal competence, intellectual competence and technical competence to the employability of the teacher education graduates. Part IV - This part of the questionnaire elicited the employability problems encountered by the graduates in job hunting.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Personal Profile of the BEED and BSED Graduates

The personal profile of the graduates was thoroughly described on the succeeding figures namely: Figure 1 for the age, Figure 1 for the sex, Figure 3 for the civil status, Figure 4 for the place of residence, Figure 5 for the place of work, Figure 6 for the year graduated, Figure 7 for the course/field of specialization, Figure 8 for the eligibility, Figure 9 for the honors received and Figure 10 for the advanced education.

Age

It can be observed from Figure 1 that there are three brackets for the age of the alumni both for the BEED and BSED. The different brackets are as follows: from 25 years old and below; 26 years old to 30 years old and 31 years old and above. From these brackets, most of the alumni fall in the second bracket (26 years old to 30 years old). This means that alumni started schooling on the right or required age and likewise, finished their course on the time frame allotted for a particular course. Considering that about seven (7) years were added to the age of the last batch which is covered by this study, it is correct to say that the respondents vary their age remarkably as shown in the average mean of their age which is 27.22 and the standard deviation of 5.26. The respondents of this study are young in terms of their age yet they are full of enthusiasm to impart what they gained in their exposure in the school.

Figure 1: A Vertical Bar Graph showing the Distribution in terms of Age Range of the BEED and BSED Programs Alumni of the Northwest Samar State University (NwSSU) of Calbayog City

Figure 2: A Vertical Bar Graph showing the Distribution in terms of Sex of the BEED and BSED Programs Alumni of the Northwest Samar State University (NwSSU) of Calbayog City

Sex

From the Figure 2, it is clearly deduced that education courses, particularly BEED and BSED is a female-dominated course because out of 164 BEED respondents, there were 132 female and only 32 male while out of 71 BSED respondents, there were 47 female and only 24 male.

Civil Status

Based on the Figure 3, there are greater number of single alumni both for BEED and BSED. Out of 164 BEED respondents, there are 95 who are still single, 68 are already married and 1 is widow while data from BSED respondents says that out of 71 respondents, there are 44 who are still single, and the remaining 27 are already

Figure 3: A Vertical Bar Graph showing the Distribution in terms of Civil Status of the BEED and BSED Programs Alumni of the Northwest Samar State University (NwSSU) of Calbayog City

Place of Work

From the result shown in Figure 5, the work place of the respondents of this study are classified into places within city proper, places outside city proper but within Calbayog and places outside Calbayog City. For the BEED respondents, out of 164 alumni, there are 20 who worked in places within the city proper, 108 alumni worked in places outside city proper but within Calbayog, 24 alumni worked in places outside Calbayog City and 12 alumni remarked no answer while from BSED respondents, out of 71 respondents, there are 16 alumni worked in the city proper, 42 alumni worked in places outside city proper but within Calbayog and 2 alumni answered blankly.

Figure 5: A Vertical Bar Graph showing the Distribution in terms of Place of Work of the BEED and BSED Programs Alumni of the Northwest Samar State University (NwSSU) of Calbayog City

Course/Field of Specialization

The pie graph below showed a comparison between the BEED and BSED courses and it turned out that the former is an in - demand course. From the total respondents of 235 graduates, there were 164 BEED alumni and only 71 BSED alumni.

married.

Place of Residence

Figure 4 described the place of residence of the respondent alumni of this study and it is categorized as places within the city proper, places outside city proper but within Calbayog and places outside Calbayog City. From BEED respondents, out of 164 alumni, there are 50 who lived in places within city proper, 84 alumni lived in places outside city proper but within Calbayog, and 30 alumni lived in places outside Calbayog City. On the other hand, out 71 BSED respondents, there are 14 alumni who lived in places within city proper, 44 alumni lived in places outside city proper but within Calbayog, and 13 alumni lived in places outside Calbayog City.

Figure 4: A Vertical Bar Graph showing the Distribution in terms of Place of Residence of the BEED and BSED Programs Alumni of the Northwest Samar State University (NwSSU) of Calbayog City

Year Graduated

From Figure 6, it can be described that there are school years wherein the College produced a number of graduates. This bar graph is categorized by school year for both BEED and BSED respondents. Out of 164 BEED respondents, there are 39 alumni for SY 2005 – 2006, 40 alumni for SY 2006 – 2007, 34 for SY 2007 -2008, 27 alumni for SY 2008 – 2009 and 24 alumni for SY 2009 – 2010. On the other hand, out of 71 BSED respondents, there are 20 alumni for SY 2005 – 2006, 16 alumni for SY 2006 – 2007, 10 alumni for SY 2007 – 2008, 9 alumni for SY 2008 – 2009 and 16 alumni for SY 2009 – 2010.

Figure 6: A Vertical Bar Graph showing the Distribution in terms of Year of Graduation of the BEED and BSED Programs Alumni of the Northwest Samar State University (NwSSU) of Calbayog City

Eligibility

As seen from Figure 8, most of the graduates were already with eligibilities or licenses. For the BEED respondents, out of 163 alumni, there were 114 Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET) passers, and 49 alumni are non-passers while for BSED respondents, out of 71 alumni, there were 45 LET passers, and 26 non-passers.

Figure 7: A Pie Graph showing the Distribution in terms of Course of the of the Alumni of the Northwest Samar State University (NwSSU) of Calbayog City

Honors Received

Figure 9 presented the graduates who received honors during their graduation. For the BEED respondents, out of 164 graduates, there were 18 cum laude, 1 magna cum laude and 145 non – honors while for BSED respondents, out of 71 graduates, there were 14 cum laude, 3 magna cum laude and 54 non – honors.

Figure 8: A Vertical Bar Graph showing the Distribution in terms of the Eligibility of the BEED and BSED Alumni of the Northwest Samar State University (NwSSU) of Calbayog City

Advanced Education

From Figure 10, it can be seen that there were graduates who pursued advanced studies and enrolled in the Graduate School. For the BEED respondents, out of 164

Figure 9: A Vertical Bar Graph showing the Distribution in terms of Honors Received of the BEED and BSED Programs Alumni of the Northwest Samar State University (NwSSU) of Calbayog City

alumni, there were 8 alumni who are full-fledged Master’s Degree holders, 2 alumni have completed academic requirements (CAR) in the master’s degree, 25 with MA units and 129 decided not to pursue yet advanced studies.

Employment Status of Graduates

The employment status of graduates as to work status, nature of work, type of employment, manner of getting the job and waiting time after graduation were described in the following tabular and graphical presentations. The sub – ideas were also discussed in the following presentations.

Work Status

From Figure 11 below, it can be deduced that most of the graduates produced by the College landed a job after graduation. For the BEED respondents, out of 164 graduates, there were 158 alumni who were already employed and 6 alumni were not yet employed. On the other hand, out of 71 BSED respondents, there were 69 alumni who were already employed and only 2 alumni who were not yet employed. Looking closely the over-all result of the status of employment, both for BEED and BSED courses, graduates have better chances of employment as the figure suggested that out 235 respondents, there were 227 (96.60%) alumni who are already employed and only 8 (3.40%) alumni who are not yet employed.

Figure 10: A Vertical Bar Graph showing the Distribution in terms of the Eligibility of the BEED and BSED Alumni of the Northwest Samar State University (NwSSU) of Calbayog City

Figure 11: A Pie Graph showing the Employment Status in terms of Number Employed of the BEED and BSED Programs Alumni of the Northwest Samar State University (NwSSU) of Calbayog City

Initial Work Experience.

Table 1 below presented the distribution of the employment status of the BEED and BSED graduates in terms of first job after college. Based on the result,

out of 164 BEED respondents, there were 83 (50.61%) graduates who answered that “YES” it is the first job after college, 77 (46.95%) graduates who answered that “NO” it is not the first job after college and 4 (2.44%) graduates who answered blankly.

Table 1: Distribution of the Employment Status of the BEED and BSED Programs Alumni of the Northwest Samar State University of Calbayog City in terms of First Job in College

Response	BEED (N = 164)		BSED (N = 71)		Over-all (N =235)	
	f	%	f	%	f	%
Yes	83	50.61	29	40.84	112	47.66
No	77	46.95	40	56.34	117	49.79
No response	4	2.44	2	28.57	6	2.55
Total	164	100.00	71	100.00	235	100.00

On the other hand, out of 71 BSED respondents, there were 29 (40.84%) graduates who answered “YES” it is the first job after college, 40 (56.34%) graduates who answered “NO” it is not the first job after college and 2 (28.57%) graduates who remarked no response. With the over-all result, out of 235 respondents, there were 112 (47.66%) graduates who said it is the first job after college, 117 (49.79%) graduates who said it is not the first job after college and only 6 (2.55%) graduates who did not take any response.

Employment Status

This Table 2 presented the distribution of employment status of the BEED and BSED respondents on the work that they have at the present or during the conduct of the study. The status of the employment is described as permanent, temporary, contractual and others. For the BEED respondents, out of 158 alumni, 93 (58.90%) remarked that they are already permanent, 9 (5.70%) mentioned they are only temporary, 49 (31%) stated they are contractual and 7 (4.4%) pointed out others. On the other hand, out of 69 BSED respondents, 41 (59.40%) remarked that they are already permanent, 7 (10.10%) mentioned they are only temporary, 19 (27.50%) stated

Table 2: Distribution of the Employment Status of the BEED and BSED Programs Alumni of the Northwest Samar State University of Calbayog City

Status	BEED (N = 164)		BSED (N = 71)		Over-all (N =235)	
	f	%	f	%	f	%
Permanent	93	58.90	41	59.40	134	59.03
Temporary	9	5.70	7	10.10	16	7.05
Contractual	49	31.00	19	27.50	68	29.96
Other	7	4.40	2	2.90	9	3.96
Total	158	100.00	69	100.00	227	100.00

they are contractual and 29 (2.90%) pointed out others for their status. Thus, for the over-all, out of 227 respondents, 134 (59.03%) graduates are already permanent, 16 (7.05%) graduates are still temporary, 68 (29.96%) graduates are contractual and 9 (3.96%) are classified for others.

Nature of Work

Table 3: Distribution of the Employment Status of the BEED and BSED Programs Alumni of the Northwest Samar State University of Calbayog City in terms of Nature of Work

Nature	BEED (N = 164)		BSED (N = 71)		Over-all (N =235)	
	f	%	F	%	f	%
Teaching the Major Field	91	55.49	34	47.89	125	53.19
Teaching Not the Major Field	52	31.71	29	40.84	81	34.47
Not Teaching	13	7.93	6	8.45	19	8.08
No Response	8	4.88	2	2.82	10	4.26
Total	164	100.00	71	100.00	235	100.00

to be lucky because they were teaching their major field, 52 (31.71%) graduates answered they were teaching but not on their major field, 13 (7.93%) graduates confessed they were not teaching and 8 (4.88%) graduates answered blankly. On the other hand, out of 71 BSED respondents, 34 (47.89%) graduates disclosed that they were teaching their major field, 29 (40.84%) graduates stated they were teaching but not in the major field, 6 (8.45%) graduates

Table 3 showed the distribution of the employment status of the BEED and BSED in terms of the nature of work as to whether the graduates were teaching on the major field, teaching not on the major field and not teaching at all. For the BEED respondents, out of 164 alumni, there were 91 (55.49%) graduates who admitted

divulged that they were not yet teaching and 2 (2.82%) graduates also answered blankly.

Type of Employment

From Figure 12 below, it can be gleaned that there were different types of employer the graduates had for their employment. It can be classified as government, private and others.

Figure 12: A Vertical Bar Graph showing the Distribution in terms of Status of Employment of the BEED and BSED Programs Alumni of the Northwest Samar State University (NwSSU) of Calbayog City

Manner of Getting the Job

Table 4 below showed the distribution on the manner of getting the job of the BEED and BSED graduates after their graduation. Among the responses were as follows: response to an advertisement, as walk in applicant, information from friends, arranged by the school's

placement officer, recommended by someone, recruited by employer, through application letter, job fair and others. Among the responses, very prominent were the answers on the employment through application letter and recommendation by someone.

Waiting Time After Graduation

Table 4. Distribution on the Manner of Getting the Job of the BEED and BSED Programs Alumni of the Northwest Samar State University of Calbayog City in terms of Nature of Work

Nature	BEED (N = 164)		BSED (N = 71)		Over-all (N =235)	
	f	%	F	%	f	%
Response to an advertisement	1	0.61	0	0.00	1	0.61
As walk in applicant	24	14.63	10	6.10	34	20.73
Information from friends	16	9.76	8	4.88	24	14.63
Arranged by school's job placement officer	6	3.66	2	1.22	8	4.88
Recommended by Someone	36	21.95	12	7.32	48	29.27
Recruited by employer	3	1.83	5	3.05	8	4.88
Through application Letter	69	42.07	32	19.51	101	61.59
Job fair	2	1.22	0	0.00	2	1.22
Others	7	4.27	2	1.22	9	5.49
Total	164	100.00	71	100.00	235	100.00

Table 5 showed the mean and standard deviation on the waiting time that the graduates be able to get a job right after graduation. The result revealed that the BEED respondents have an average mean of 1.01 years while the BSED respondents have 0.86 years on their waiting time before they had a job.

Problems Encountered by the Graduates In Job

Table 5: Mean and Standard Deviation on the Waiting Time After Graduation (In Years) of the BEED and BSED Programs Alumni of the Northwest Samar State University of Calbayog City

Course/Alumni	\bar{x}	Standard Deviation
BEED	1.01 years	0.98 years
BSED	0.86 years	1.14 years
Over-all	0.97 years	1.04 years

Hunting

Table 6 showed the ranking of the problems encountered by the BEED and BSED respondents on the course of finding profitable employment for their profession. The respondents, both BEED and BSED graduates freely identified the nominal problems relative to their employment.

Table 6: Ranking of the Problems Encountered by the BEED and BSED Alumni of the Northwest Samar State University of Calbayog City

Problems	BEED		BSED		OVER-ALL	
	f	rank	f	rank	f	rank
Lack of financial capacity to look for a job in big cities	97	1	50	1	147	1
Lack of financial capacity to allocate amount for transportation	88	2	41	2	129	2
Lack of financial capacity to prepare the pertinent documents	80	3	40	3	120	3
Many applicants but few available vacancies	72	4	37	4.5	109	4
No vacancy in the desired type of job	69	5	37	4.5	106	5
Strong familial political affiliation	63	6	35	6	98	6
Low salaries and benefits	62	7	34	7	96	7
Lack of training for the available job	55	8	23	9	78	8
No information available as to job opportunities	44	9	22	11	66	9
Pressure from superior	41	10	23	9	64	10
Adverse peer influence	32	12	18	12	50	11.5
High preference to honor graduates	27	15.5	23	9	50	11.5
High demand for professional growth	33	11	14	15	47	13
Low family image or reputation	28	14	16	13	44	14

From the result below particularly with the BEED respondents, out of 164 graduates, 97 alumni rated the first check box making it to be the rank 1 which described as “lack of financial capacity to look for a job in big cities”, followed by the third check box wherein 88 alumni rated making it to be the rank 2 which described as “limited budget for transportation” and the second check box was identified as the rank 3 by the BEED respondents. Even considering the other group's perceptions about the problems encountered in job hunting, they are consistent which eventually resulted also with the same arrangement of problems based on the rank. For both groups, BEED and BSED, rank 1 is problem on lack of financial capacity to look for a job in big cities, rank 2 is the problem on limited budget for transportation expenses and rank 3 is the problem on limited resources for preparation of pertinent papers and documents. Therefore, the major problem of the graduates encountered during their job hunting is on the financial aspect. Graduates humbly admitted that their chances to employment were hampered by the monetary considerations.

CONCLUSION

Lack of financial capacity to prepare needed IMs	28	13	15	14	43	15
Limited attendance to trainings and seminars	27	15.5	12	17	39	16
Poor time management	19	17	12	17	31	17
Lack of appropriate eligibilities	18	18	12	17	28	18
Diversity of career challenges	16	19	10	21	26	19
Lack of motivation from family and relatives	14	20	10	21	24	20
No connection or “padrino”	9	23.5	6	24	21	21
Poor physical health condition	12	21	10	21	20	22
Unfavorable relations with fellow mentors	10	22	9	22	19	23
Indifference of family members towards teaching	9	23.5	8	23	15	24
Others, please specify	0	25	0	25	0	25

The graduates of the College are potential partners in nation building since they are still young, enthusiastic, receptive to innovations and immersed to the grass root-level of education. Also, the course offering of the College is commendable since it caters the need of the locality and demand for employment opportunities thereby giving better chances for the graduates to find job and eventually alleviating the economic condition of every citizen. The kind of orientation, learning experiences as well as the curricular offerings of the graduates in the College make them qualified to the diverse job opportunities in the real world. Finally, the problem of graduates on financial aspect is not a new thing. Therefore, this is a challenge to everybody on how to battle such and instead, transform this problem into a motivation so that the living condition will now be improved.

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